

D. Raoult and hydroxychloroquine

A case study about research integrity

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Short version

Very early on in the COVID-19 pandemic, a controversy started regarding the use of hydroxychloroquine as a potential COVID-19 treatment. A French professor claimed that hydroxychloroquine combined with an antibiotic could inhibit the new coronavirus in a few days. The methodology of his study was immediately questioned by other scientists, but emergency use authorization was granted in the US and in France. Whilst the authorizations were soon withdrawn, relevant papers retracted and the professor investigated for scientific fraud, some legal cases he started are still ongoing in 2025 and the fraud had deep public health consequences during the pandemic and beyond.

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Very early on in the COVID-19 pandemic, a controversy started to develop, related to the use of **hydroxychloroquine as a COVID-19 treatment**.

Professor Didier Raoult of the *Institut Hospitalo-Universitaire, Méditerranée, Infection* (IHU-MI) in Marseilles made headlines at the end of February 2020, through a video in which he announced the "endgame" against the new coronavirus from Wuhan in China.

He claimed that hydroxychloroquine, a synthetic derivative of quinine prescribed for several decades against malaria, combined with the azithromycin antibiotic would be the **lethal weapon to inhibit the virus** in a few days.

Prof. Didier Raoult on YouTube talking about hydroxychloroquine in February 2020

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cuB0NO5piE8>

In one of his first communications on studies carried out at IHU-MI, Raoult stated that out of 24 patients treated with azithromycin and hydroxychloroquine at his institution, 75% had a negative viral load after six days, **proof of a breakthrough discovery** of a COVID 19 cure.

He submitted a paper on 16 March 2020, which was published online 4 days later (Gautret et al, 2020). Multiple critics emerged promptly, challenging the methodology of the study and the interpretation of the results (Zongo, 2020).

Study results were questioned

For instance, on 24 March 2020, **Elisabeth Bik** published a blog noting that six patients had been dropped from the study, one of whom one had died and three had been transferred to intensive care. This, she argued, could have **skewed the results** (O' Grady, 2024). Heated public arguments ensued between Bik and Raoult's teams and their respective supporters on

social media, leading to a lawsuit against Bik in April 2021 (Larousserie, 2021). **In 2024, the prosecutor found that Bik had no case to answer** (Singh Chawla, 2024).

The intervention of US President **Donald Trump** on 19 March 2020, in support of this experimental treatment fuelled the controversy, despite the US Food and Drug Administration's (FDA's) prudent stance on hydroxychloroquine's efficacy and safety. Whilst the FDA issued an Emergency Use Authorization on 28 March 2020, it was revoked on 15 June 2020 (FDA, 2020) as new data became available.

Similarly, hydroxychloroquine was given a **temporary approval status in France** on March 26, 2020 and this temporary approval was withdrawn two months later (Morin, 2020a).

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Research ethics committee challenged

From the beginning of the controversy, D. Raoult challenged the role and processes of the National Consultative Ethics Committee for Life Sciences and Health (CCNE) and of the Ethical Review Committees charged with evaluating research projects (Raoult, 2020). He painted them as rigid defenders of “orthodox” science and obsolete methodologies, often suspect of conflicts of interests, that **allegedly stood in the way of innovative research**.

Significant media and public interest

National and international press articles covered this controversy in great detail over the ensuing months (Cabut, 2020). Many scientists reacted to the controversy and took issue with the non-science based “populist” stance of Raoult (Schultz and Blanchard, 2022; Editorial,

2021). Over time, a scientific consensus emerged which proved that early claims of azithromycin plus hydroxychloroquine's efficacy and safety for a COVID-19 treatment could not be substantiated (Morin, 2020b).

Allegation of scientific fraud

In 2022, investigations launched by French government authorities raised a series of accusations of scientific fraud and unethical behaviour at IHU-MI. These triggered legal action (Larousserie, 2022), based on "serious dysfunctions of the IHU-MI concerning the quality of its research and care activities" and "serious shortcomings" *and procedures* "not in accordance with the regulations on research involving human beings (RIPH), particularly on the ethical level".

Raoult publicly responded to these accusations questioning the medical and scientific competence of the experts and **launching multiple legal proceedings**, several of which are ongoing at the time of writing (March 2025). He retired from his position at IHU-MI in the summer of 2022.

Retractions

In September 2022, the American Society of Microbiology placed expressions of concern on six of Raoult's papers for "scientific misconduct investigation" (Marcus, 2022) and in December 2022 PLOS flagged nearly 50 out of more than 100 of his papers for potential research ethics violations (Kincaid, 2022). After **a series of scientific papers retracts**, the initial March 2020 paper from Raoult's team that triggered the fight over hydroxychloroquine was retracted in December 2024, by the International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents (Gautret et al., 2025).

Conclusion

Overall, controversies around hydroxychloroquine during the first months of the pandemic initiated by Raoult had far-reaching consequences globally, fuelling controversies around "miracle cures" for COVID, challenging the legitimacy of health and scientific institutions and political decision-makers in crises situations, and laying the foundations of anti-vaccine and other misinformation movements, all of which had **deep public health consequences** during the pandemic and beyond.

The main points from this case study are:

- *Ethical communication on "scientific discoveries" in crises situations*
- *Scientists' usage of media and contribution to controversies*
- *Integrity of publications*
- *Ethical misconduct during clinical trials*

Case Study Author

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